

REGULATORY ENVIRONMENT: UK & US

◀ DISTANCE LEARNING WITH eSCRIPT ▶

October, 2013/2014

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	3
Overview of General Regulatory Environment.....	4
Financial Services and Banking Sector: Deregulate Or Self-Regulate.....	6
Hedge-fund framework in UK and US.....	6
Corporate governance in banking in UK and US.....	10
Environmental Regulatory Framework	12
Environmental Enforcements in UK.....	13
US Environmental Regime, Standards and Enforcements.....	14
US Agency Struggles.....	15
Intellectual Property, FDI and Trade	16
Conclusion.....	17
BIBLIOGRAPHY	18

Introduction

The idea of “regulation” is generally that of a rule or directive maintained by an authority¹. In this sense, regulation could be defined to encompass all ‘rules’ where the rules are established and enforced by the State or by a statutorily empowered commission that governs the interactions/transactions between economic agents². As the early European economy moved from a simple agricultural based to a mercantile and industrial economy, the interpretation of “regulation” evolved as well (Chatfield,1977). Enterprises could only be formed by specific acts of Parliament until Joint Stock Companies Act of 1844 was enacted³. The doctrine of *Laissez-faire*⁴ became an integral part of the 19th century European liberalism where the government agency was viewed as merely a passive policeman, protecting private property but not interfering with the affairs of its citizens. The United States instituted its own principles of nationalism driven by concerns over socioeconomic independence from Europeans. While there were always forces that favored a *laissez-fair* form of governance in the US until the early 19th century, the *Lochner v New York*⁵ case in 1905 marked the “progressive”⁶ departure from “laissez-fair constitutionalism” and ushered the “Lochner era” of increased constitutional authority of the US states to exercise police powers⁷.

The historic development of governance philosophies in the United States and European countries has been divergent owing generally to the development of property rights regimes and remnants of pre-industrial monarchy authoritarianism⁸ in Europe contrasted by the supremacy of the Constitution in the United States. Modern discourse on nation-state governance has been dominated by discussions of a linear perspective of regulation proposed by Gunningham and Rees⁹ as “a spectrum ranging from a

1 See 'regulation', Oxford English Dictionary, <http://www.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/regulation?q=regulation>

2 M Weber *Economy and Society: An outline of interpretative sociology* in G Roth and C Wittich (eds) (Univ. California Press Berkeley 1978) p 82

3 Josephine Maltby, *UK joint stock companies legislation 1844-1900: accounting publicity and "mercantile caution"*, *Accounting History* 1998 3: 9 DOI: 10.1177/103237329800300102, Sage Publications. Available at: <http://ach.sagepub.com/content/3/1/9.full.pdf>

4 See definition at Encyclopedia Britannica : <http://www.britannica.com/EBchecked/topic/328028/laissez-faire>

5 198 U.S. 45, *Lochner v. New York* (No. 292), Cornell University Law School, Legal Information Institute, http://www.law.cornell.edu/supct/html/historics/USSC_CR_0198_0045_ZS.html

6 The term “progressive” in this context refers to the legal dimension of the early twentieth- century Progressive movement, rather than contemporary left-leaning political “progressives.”

7 Matthew J. Lindsay, *IN SEARCH OF “LAISSEZ-FAIRE CONSTITUTIONALISM”*, *Harvard Law Review Forum*, Vol 123:55, Available at: http://www.harvardlawreview.org/media/pdf/vol123_forum_lindsay.pdf

8 Hans Ulrich Jessurun d’Oliveira, *“The State of the European Union’s Monarchies The EU and Its Monarchies: Influences and Frictions”*, *European Constitutional Law Review*, 8: 63–81, 2012, Cambridge Journals, Available at: <http://www.cesruc.org/uploads/soft/130308/1-13030QFQ8.pdf>

9 Gunningham, N., and Rees. J., (1997), *Industry Self Regulation, An Institutional Perspective*, Law and Policy, Vol. 19,

detailed government command and control regulation to “pure” self regulation”¹⁰. The OECD classifies regulations into three categories: economic, social and administrative¹¹. Therefore, regulations are not only aimed at specific social or economic goals and objectives, but also stipulate costs and perceived benefits. Regulatory reform are often needed to improve regulatory quality in order to enhance the performance, cost-effectiveness, and legal quality of regulations in order to achieve macro socioeconomic goals. These reforms are either activist (US Civil Rights movement of 1960¹² or Common Agriculture Policy (CAP) in England¹³) or reactionary (Dodd-Frank Act¹⁴).

This paper will explore the general regulatory environment currently dominating the United Kingdom and the United States by drawing a comparison of the developmental influences, style of regulation, record of enforcements, and compliance approaches. The paper examines the general body of regulators and related legislative statutes empowering them with a particularly closer look at the financial and environmental regulations observed in the UK and the US.

Overview of General Regulatory Environment

The US model of regulation has largely been adversarial, and science-based in comparison to UK where the majority of the models were consensual and shifting towards a corporatist style of policy-making¹⁵. The US model is a Hobbesian one originally designed to avoid emergence of monarchy-like powers. Until the 1980s United States regulated by rule-making through various processes and then informed regulated entities. The regulated entities and interest groups had the opportunity to comment on the proposal. By Mid-1990s, regulation-by-litigation began to be used by agencies to enforce and create new substantive obligations for the regulated¹⁶. The 1998 settlement between the attorneys

Issue, p. 363-414

10 Gunningham, N., and Rees, J., (1997), *Industry Self Regulation, An Institutional Perspective*, Law and Policy, Vol. 19, Issue, p. 363-414; see also Bartle, I., and Vass, P., (2005) *Self Regulation and The Regulatory State: A Survey of Policy and Practice*, Research Report 17, Centre for the Study of Regulated Industries, School of Management, University of Bath, England

11 OECD, “*Indicators of Product Market Regulation (PMR)*”, <http://www.oecd.org/eco/reform/indicatorsofproductmarketregulationpmr.htm>

12 “Regulatory Federalism: Policy, Process, Impact and Reform”, Advisory Commission on Intergovernmental Relations, Washington, D.C, *Available at:* <http://www.library.unt.edu/gpo/acir/Reports/brief/B-7.pdf>

13 Gov.UK, “*CAP reform in England: Status report on direct payments*”, <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/cap-reform-in-england-status-report-on-direct-payments>

14 US Government, *Dodd-Frank Wall Street Reform and Consumer Protection Act* <http://www.sec.gov/about/laws/wallstreetreform-cpa.pdf>

15 Ortwin Renn, Commentary on article by Raagnar E. Lofstedt and David Vogel, “*The Changing Character of Regulation: A Comparison of Europe and the United States*”, *Risk Analysis* Vol. 21, No. 3, 2001, *Available at:* https://courses.washington.edu/eulaw09/supplemental_readings/lofstedt_vogel_changing.pdf

16 Andrew P. Morriss, Bruce Yandle, Andrew Dorchak, “*Choosing How to Regulate*”, *Harvard Environmental Law*

general of forty-six states and several major cigarette manufacturers is a prominent example of regulation-by-litigation of that time¹⁷. Similarly, in 1998, a heavy-duty diesel producer signed a \$1 billion settlement with the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) which included imposition of emission standards that the Clean Air Act (CAA) prevented EPA from imposing directly¹⁸. However, the massive costs of litigation maybe averted by the agencies and the regulated entities through regulation-by-negotiation formally authorized by Negotiated Rulemaking Act of 1990¹⁹, and the Administrative Dispute Resolution Act of 1996²⁰.

The member states of the European Union do not have the same threat of litigation as that exists in the United States. Kelmen would argue that European nations are not self-assertive like the Americans (Kelman,1981). The consensual style in UK has been a “closed-door” approach to regulation (Brikman et al., 1985; Vogel,1986) while transparency has long been part of the U.S regulatory model since the 1946 Administrative Procedures Act²¹. The 'club government' in the UK characterized by oligarchic, informal, and secretive operations is a legacy of the old Victorian regulatory state (Moran, 2003)²². The Victorian era had created public and private institutions, including: ‘the Factory Inspectors; the Poor Law Commissioners; the Prison Inspectorate; the Railway Board; These institutions were shaped by cooperative relationships between the regulator and the regulatee; the private and the public. The burgeoning of regulatory instruments along with rising unemployment and monetary inflation provoked the conservative government of Margaret Thatcher to lift compliance burdens through deregulation of the product and the labour market²³. However, over the years the general public's trust of the authorities has eroded with food and environmental disasters such as the “Mad Cow Disease”(BSE)²⁴, and Piper Alpha (1988)²⁵ incidents, and the UK crisis of the 1970s²⁶. It should also

Review, Vol. 29. 2005. Available at: http://www.law.harvard.edu/students/orgs/elr/vol29_1/morriss.pdf

17 See National Association of Attorneys General, Master Settlement Agreement at 14–36 (describing restrictions on defendants’ behavior agreed to as part of the settlement), at http://www.naag.org/upload/1032468605_cigmsa.pdf (last visited Oct. 16, 2004)

18 Andrew P. Morriss, Bruce Yandle & Andrew Dorchak, Regulation by Litigation: EPA’s Regulation of Heavy-Duty Diesel Engines, 56 Admin. L. Rev. 403 (2004)

19 Pub. L. No. 101-648, 104 Stat. 4969 (codified as amended at 5 U.S.C. §§ 561–570 (2000))

20 Pub. L. No. 104-320, 110 Stat. 3870, 3873-74 (codified at 5 U.S.C. § 561 (2000))

21 APA, 5 U.S.C. § 553(c) (2000)

22 Moran, Michael, *The British Regulatory State: High Modernism and Hyper Innovation*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2003, P 31-42

23 Matthews, K., Minford, P., Nickell, S., & Helpman, E. (1987). Mrs Thatcher’s economic policies 1979-1987. *Economic Policy*, 2(5), 59–101

24 Christoph Strünck, “*Why is there no mad cow disease in the United States? Comparing the politics of food safety in Europe and the U.S.*”, Haas School of Business, University of California, Berkeley, <http://ies.berkeley.edu/pubs/workingpapers/PRI-1-Madcow.pdf>

25 Christine Parker, Vibeke Lehmann Nielse, “*Explaining Compliance: Business Responses to Regulation*”

26 The Economist, “Worst of times, best of times”, <http://www.economist.com/node/17090761>, Sept. 23, 2010; See also,

be noted, that the general distrust of authorities has been disseminated into EU member states due to emergence of signs of corruption at the EU level and the dissatisfaction with the European Commission (EC). The European Commissions' civil servants are not democratically elected by citizens of the member states, and in 1999 the EC undermined its own legitimacy following a scandal of misuse of funds, and administrative incompetence²⁷. This has led to strong influence on UK environmental regulation through activist reform.

In theory, both the US and the UK governments have been on a pendulum swing between no regulation, self-regulation and legislative co-regulation by instituting distinctive procedural agents of risk assessments and risk management²⁸. This is particularly the case when we examine the developments in the hedge-fund and banking industry in both jurisdictions.

Financial Services and Banking Sector: Deregulate Or Self-Regulate

Hedge-fund framework in UK and US

Hedge funds were designed to notoriously fall through the Security Exchange Commission (SEC) regulation to offer greater investment versatility²⁹. UK Economic Secretary to the Treasury, Ed Balls, summarizes hedge funds as instruments that “provide liquidity, help markets price assets more accurately and drive financial innovation”³⁰. The hedge fund industry grew quickly with estimated \$50 billion invested in 1993, and about \$1 trillion by 2006³¹. Hedge funds are not only difficult to classify because of boundaries with other investment activities, but are also exempt from full disclosure which was reflected in three respected index providers' varying valuation of the hedge-fund market in 2007:\$1.25, \$1.74, \$2.48 trillion³². Apart from the possibility of outright fraud in false fund size

State of Emergency: The Way We Were. Britain, 1970–1974. By Dominic Sandbrook

27 Heyvaert, V. (1999). The changing role of science in environmental regulatory decision-making in the European Union. *Law and European Affairs*, 9, 426- 443.

28 Ragnar E. Lofsted, and David Vogel, “*The Changing Character of Regulation: A Comparison of Europe and the United States*”, *Risk Analysis*, Vol.21, No.3, 2001. Available at: https://courses.washington.edu/eulaw09/supplemental_readings/lofstedt_vogel_changing.pdf

29 J.W. Verret, Dr Jones and the Raiders of Lost Capital; Hedge Fund Regulation, Part II, A Self-Regulation Proposal, 32 *DEL. J. CORP. L* 799, 803 (2007)

30 Ed Balls, MP, Economic Secretary to the Treasury, Speech at the FSA Principles-based Regulation Conference (Apr. 23, 2007), available at http://www.hm-treasury.gov.uk/newsroom_and_speeches/press/2007/press_48_07.cfm

31 President’s working group on financial markets, hedge funds, leverage, and the lessons of long-term capital management 1 (1999) (hereinafter pwg 1999 report), Available at <http://www.treas.gov/press/releases/reports/hedgefund.pdf>

32 Alistair MacDonald & Margot Patrick, Hedge Funds: Leveraging the Numbers — Size Can Be Deceiving When Borrowed Money Is Added to Calculation, *WALL ST. J.*, Nov. 24, 2007, at B1

reporting to attract investors, the primary method of inflating the size is to include borrowed money as an asset. In 2007, Fairfield Greenwich Group reported itself as a \$15 billion fund but that included \$2 billion of borrowed money³³. The philosophy that “sophisticated” investors in hedge-funds can fend for themselves, understand the risks, and do not need to be regulated externally appears to be the prevailing rationale in both the UK and the US³⁴. However, the secretive nature of hedge funds creates information asymmetries, and opportunities to falsify performance figures that has also resulted in criminal prosecutions. Daniel Marino, CFO of Bayou Management was sentenced 20 years in prison for \$400 million in investor fraud; John Whittier of Wood River Capital Management was sentenced to 3 years in prison, and fined \$5.5 million³⁵. The UK Serious Fraud Office (SFO) prosecuted Weaving Capital (UK) Limited on charges of six fraud offences awarding \$450 million in damages but no prison sentence³⁶.

The UK financial regulatory structure was created by the Financial Services Authority (FSA)³⁷. FSA has had been very vocal about regulating the hedge funds compared to the US authorities and oversaw the marketing of hedge funds and regarded them as “unregulated collective investment schemes,” and as such they may not be marketed to the general public and only to private customers in limited circumstances³⁸. Hedge funds are not physically located in the UK for tax reasons, therefore, FSA (now Financial Conduct Authority (FCA)³⁹) regulates the UK-based hedge fund managers who engage in “regulated activities” and must seek authorization to do so under the Financial Services and Markets Act 2000. The FCA recognizes that it is not territorially able to regulate the “systems and controls of the underlying hedge fund[s]” hence it is directed at regulating managers⁴⁰. In litigation, costs are paid by the “loser” (*FSA v. Simon Treacher and FSA v. Steven Harrison*⁴¹) although “shadow

33 John Horsfield-Bradbury, “Hedge Fund Self-Regulation in the US and the UK”, April, 2008, Harvard Law Review, Available at: http://www.law.harvard.edu/programs/corp_gov/papers/Brudney2008_Horsfield-Bradbury.pdf

34 Troy A. Paredes, On the Decision to Regulate Hedge Funds: The SEC’s Regulatory Philosophy, Style, and Mission, 2006 U. ILL. L. REV. 975, at 991 n.62.; also See *Supra* note 30

35 Chad Bray, Bayou’s Ex-Finance Chief Sentenced to 20 Years, WALL ST. J., Jan. 30, 2008; Former Head of Wood River Is Sentenced, WALL ST. J., Oct. 16, 2007

36 Reuters, Laurence Fletcher, “UPDATE 1-UK’s SFO charges Weaving fund founder with fraud”, <http://www.reuters.com/article/2012/12/14/weaving-sfo-idUSL5E8NE8NV20121214>; See also, SFO.gov, “Weaving Hedge Fund: criminal charges”, <http://www.sfo.gov.uk/press-room/latest-press-releases/press-releases-2012/weaving-hedge-fund--criminal-charges-.aspx>

37 FSA, Who We Regulate, <http://www.fsa.gov.uk/pages/About/What/Who/index.shtml>

38 FSA, DISCUSSION PAPER 16, HEDGE FUNDS AND THE FSA (Aug. 2002), available at <http://www.fsa.gov.uk/pubs/discussion/dp16.pdf>.

39 BBC News - Business, UK, “UK financial regulation overhauled”, March 31, 2013, <http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/business-21987829>

40 FAS Handbook, at R. 3.5.3, available at <http://fsahandbook.info/FSA/html/handbook/COBS/3/5#D182>.

41 Financial New, William Hutchings, “FSA fines fourth hedge fund manager”, 03 Feb, 2010, <http://www.efinancialnews.com/story/2010-02-03/fsa-fines-fourth-hedge-fund-manager>

litigations” have also prevailed as a way of private dispute resolution⁴². In October 2005, FSA setup a dedicated center of Hedge Fund Manager Supervision Team, and in the “2006 Feedback” report, FSA noted it “welcomed” the development of a global “industry-led...Code of Conduct”⁴³.

The FSA regulated using a principle based approach enforcing businesses to follow the “Principle of Business”⁴⁴. The scope of principles is broad enough to allow regulatory flexibility without the need to enacting legislation or even changing rules. In 2007, FSA visited a number of hedge fund managers as part of a review to assess formal control systems in place used to mitigate the risk of market abuse. The review lead to the launch of a consultation titled *Disclosure of Contracts for Difference*, in November 2007⁴⁵. During the same year, the Hedge Fund Working Group (“HFWG”) was formed by 14 UK-based hedge funds to establish a set of best practice standards for the hedge fund industry. The HFWG Final Report noted that regulation of hedge funds in the US is “less embracing” and that there is no such “set of statutory principles⁴⁶.” United Kingdom's FCA requires that an independent third party value a fund's assets and subjects hedge fund managers to high standards of reporting requirements and monitoring. It must also be noted that FCA Principles are “minimum standards,” whereas the HFWG Standards are only seen as best-practice policies.

In the United States, hedge funds have qualified as exempt under the Securities Act of 1933⁴⁷, the Securities Exchange Act of 1934⁴⁸, the Investment Company Act of 1940⁴⁹, and the Investment Advisors Act of 1940⁵⁰. U.S. regulators did not pay hedge funds much attention until the near collapse of LTCM in 1998⁵¹. Long Term Capital Management (LTCM) was a highly leveraged macro hedge

42 Angela Hayes, Pat. S. Conti and Sean Casey, “*Litigation and regulatory enforcement risk for uk based hedge fund managers – will we follow the us experience?*” Hedge Funds Review, 4 June 2009, Available at:

http://www.mayerbrown.com/files/Publication/6b108cad-71b2-4ff7-adb0-67577200567b/Presentation/PublicationAttachment/8b6add7c-7dac-4ea4-8c0a-6b8c975cf3cb/0348fin_Hedge_Fund_Journal_Article_hayes.pdf

43 FSA, FEEDBACK STATEMENT 06/2, HEDGE FUNDS: A DISCUSSION OF RISK AND REGULATORY ENGAGEMENT, FEEDBACK ON DP05/4 ¶ 1.1. (Mar. 2006), available at http://www.fsa.gov.uk/pubs/discussion/fs06_02.pdf.

44 FSA, The Principles, R. 2.1.1, available at <http://fsahandbook.info/FSA/html/handbook/PRIN/2/1>

45 FSA, CONSULTATION PAPER 07/20, DISCLOSURE OF CONTRACTS FOR DIFFERENCE (Nov. 2007), available at http://www.fsa.gov.uk/pubs/cp/cp07_20.pdf

46 HEDGE FUND WORKING GROUP (“HFWG”), HEDGE FUND STANDARDS: CONSULTATION PAPER, PART II (Oct. 2007), available at <http://www.hfwg.co.uk/files/HFWG%20Paper%20Part%202%20Final.pdf>

47 15 U.S.C. §§ 77a-77aa (2005)

48 15 U.S.C. §§ 78a-78nn (2007)

49 Investment Company Act of 1940, 15 U.S.C. §§ 80a-1-80a-64 (2007)

50 Investment Advisers Act of 1940, 15 U.S.C. § 80b-1-80b-21 (2007)

51 Franklin R. Edwards, Hedge Fund and the Collapse of Long-Term Capital Management, *Journal of Economic Perspectives* – Vol. 13, Number, 2, Spring 1999, P 189-210, Available at: http://www0.gsb.columbia.edu/faculty/fedwards/papers/Hedge_Funds_&_the_Collapse_of_LTCM.pdf

fund that had heavily speculated on the Western government and emerging bond market. The near collapse of LTCM drew the attention of US Congress which led the Security Exchange Commission (SEC) to attempt to regulate the industry statutorily. In 2004, SEC moved towards a “risk-based” approach and passed Investment Advisers Act (“Hedge Fund Rule”) to close the section 203(b) exemption which subjected majority of the hedge funds to register and be regulated under the SEC. However, in *Goldstein v. SEC*⁵², the Hedge Fund Rule was struck down as “arbitrary” by the Court of Appeals for the D.C. Circuit⁵³. Historically, US legislation allows only hedge funds to be setup for three types of investors: Non-Accredited Investor, Accredited investor, and Super-Accredited investor and the Rule attempted to include more investors as “clients” under the fold of law⁵⁴. In light of such retaliation to SEC's rule-making and the associative costs in US-style adversarial litigation, many of the Commissioners who had voted earlier on the Rule are now favoring self-regulation if it benefits the costs of unwelcome government intervention⁵⁵. Between 2004 - 2009, the SEC brought more than 100 cases involving hedge funds, according to Commissioner Elisse B. Walter⁵⁶. Unlike the UK, litigation is investor driven, example: *Fraternity Fund v. Beacon Hill Asset Management*⁵⁷ and *SEC v. Beacon Hill Asset Management LLC*⁵⁸. The SEC Commissioners have expressed willingness to follow an industry lead group such as The President’s Working Group on Financial Markets (“PWG”) which was formed in 1988 by President Reagan, and consists of the Secretary of the Treasury and the Chairmen of the SEC, the Federal Reserve and the Commodity Futures Trading Commission, or their representatives⁵⁹. While in 2007, PWG proposed a set of ten principles focused on systemic risks and investor protection as guidelines⁶⁰, the SEC *post-Goldstein* rule-making of exemptions and inclusion

52 Jeffrey m. Sneeringer, “*the lesson of goldstein v. Sec: if at first you do not succeed, regulate again?*”, Capital University Law Review, 36:1173, 2008. Available at: <https://www.google.ca/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=9&ved=0CHIQFjAI&url=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.quimbee.com%2Fcases%2Fgoldstein-v-securities-and-exchange-commission&ei=dBahUoX6DdHMkAeby4HIAQ&usg=AFQjCNEYFzYJP3QoRiakznSO2qkmlbeS2Q&sig2=2bczwbaVaZ6e8bN5LXz50g&bvm=bv.57155469,d.eW0>

53 451 F.3d 873 (D.C. Cir. 2006)

54 See *Supra* Note 33, IV.A.1.e

55 Christopher Cox, Chairman, SEC, Statement at News Conference Announcing NYSE-NASD Regulatory Merger (Nov. 28, 2006), available at <http://www.sec.gov/news/speech/2006/spch112806cc.htm>.

56 Elisse B. Walter, Testimony Concerning Securities Law Enforcement in the Current Financial Crisis Before the United States House of Representatives Committee on Financial Services. March 20, 2009

57 479 F. SUPP. 2D 349 (S.D.N.Y. 2007); Available at: <https://www.casetext.com/case/fraternity-fund-v-beacon-hill-asset-management-2/>

58 SEC, Litigation Release No. 18745A/ June 16, 2004, <http://www.sec.gov/litigation/litreleases/lr18745a.htm>

59 Exec. Order No. 12,631, 53 Fed. Reg. 9421 (Mar. 18, 1988)

60 PRESIDENT'S WORKING GROUP ON FINANCIAL MARKETS, AGREEMENT AMONG PWG AND U.S. AGENCY PRINCIPALS ON PRINCIPLES AND GUIDELINES REGARDING PRIVATE POOLS OF CAPITAL (Feb. 22, 2007), 1, available at http://www.treas.gov/press/releases/reports/hp272_principles.pdf

still remains a complex debate⁶¹.

Corporate governance in banking in UK and US

In both the countries, the banking sector is governed by international bodies such as the OECD and Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (Basel Committee) that have proposed standards on essential strategies and techniques for sound corporate governance of financial institutions⁶². While these legally non-binding international standards encourage strong macro oversight and monitoring of externalities, they also recognize and allow for diversity in jurisdiction⁶³.

In the UK, the Financial Services and Markets Act 2000 (FSMA) which incorporates Financial Services Act of 1986 essentially created the regulatory regime for banks in the UK. In May 1991, a Committee commissioned by Sir Adrian Cadbury proposed recommendations of financial controls mechanisms and responsibilities for Board of Directors for all corporations including banks. As part of other reforms undertaken by the European Commission, a Combined Code introduced changes to the board structure, and enhanced the role and responsibilities of non-executive directors⁶⁴. However compliance with Combined Code is not legally mandated by the FSA⁶⁵. Additionally, statutory anti-money-laundering requirements for financial firms were adopted under the Money Laundering Regulations of 1993⁶⁶ which requires all authorized financial institutions to have a self-certification program for anti-money-laundering compliance in place. As a result, several litigations followed, example: *Attorney-General of Zambia v Meer Care & Desai*⁶⁷, and *K Limited v National Westminster Bank*⁶⁸. Financial institutions are required to appoint a Money Laundering Reporting Officer (MLRO)

61 George Sami, “A Comparative Analysis of Hedge Fund Regulation in the United States and Europe”, Winter 2009, Issue 1, Northwestern Journal of International Law & Businesses, Available at:

<http://scholarlycommons.law.northwestern.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1685&context=njilb>

62 Basel Comm. on Banking Supervision, Enhancing Corporate Governance for Banking Organisations 5, <http://www.bis.org/publ/bcbs56.pdf> (Sept. 1999)

63 Kern Alexander, “Corporate Governance And Banking Regulation”, Working Paper 17, Cambridge Endowment for Research in Finance University of Cambridge, 2004; Available at: <http://www-cfap.jbs.cam.ac.uk/publications/downloads/wp17.pdf>

64 Reporting Council (Jan. 2003) Audit Committees Combined Code Guidance (London: 2003), <http://www.asb.org.uk/documents/pdf/acrereport.pdf>

65 Ibid, See D. The FSA’s Corporate Governance Regime

66 UK Legislation and Regulations: <http://www.icaew.com/en/library/subject-gateways/law/money-laundering/uk-legislation-and-regulations>; UK Parliament, “Money Laundering Regulations - Commons Library Standard Note”, Download at: <http://www.parliament.uk/briefing-papers/SN02592/money-laundering-regulations>

67 England and Wales Court of Appeal (Civil Division) Decisions, Neutral Citation Number: [2008] EWCA Civ 1007, <http://www.bailii.org/ew/cases/EWCA/Civ/2008/1007.html>

68 England and Wales Court of Appeal (Civil Division) Decisions, [2006] EWCA Civ 1039, Case No: 2005 2189 A3, <http://www.bailii.org/ew/cases/EWCA/Civ/2006/1039.html>

approved by the FSA. Until 2012, The UK Treasury, the FSA, and the Bank of England had mutually signed a MOU providing a division of responsibilities wherein the Treasury maintains the overall responsibility for policy and the adoption of statutory instruments, while the FSA has primary responsibility for the supervision and regulation of all financial business, and the Bank of England conducts monetary policy and surveillance of international financial markets. Since Financial Services Act 2012, structural changes have come about where Financial Services Authority (FSA) has been replaced by new regulatory structures such as Prudential Regulation Authority (PRA) and Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), and Financial Policy Committee (FPC)⁶⁹.

The US has been a much deregulated and liberal jurisdiction for the banking sector since the 1970s with its vague “safety and soundness”⁷⁰ principle generally driving banking regulations and corporate governance. This principle had traditionally given vast discretionary authority to the regulators which was later overturned by *Bellaire* case (David, 2007) and prompted the Congress to legislate US International Lending Supervision Act (ILSA) of 1983 mandating greater transparency⁷¹. Regulation-by-litigation has been the primary source of development in the US banking system. For example, the *Doolin Security Savings Bank v. F.D.I.C.*⁷², the Fourth Circuit Court of Appeals under 12 U.S.C. § 1818 (h)(2) and *FDIC v. Coughatta*⁷³ clarified how to determine if adequate risk assessment and capital adequacy has been satisfied in due process. The corporate structure and prevention of “conflict of interests” is supervised by the Board of Governors of The Federal Reserve System through the authority vested by The Bank Holding Act of 1956 (BHCA) and the Financial Services Modernization Act of 1999⁷⁴. BHCA was intended to prevent concentration of ownership and control of banking facilities⁷⁵.

In general, the UK policy empowers regulators for a long-term consultative implementation of corporate governance that incorporates disclosure and monitoring for overall financial stability. In contrast, US bank regulation is more prescriptive and attempts to devise more precise criterion. The US

69 Chartered Insurance Institute, Policy Briefing, “Towards Twin Peaks: The UK’s Emerging Regulatory Landscape (January 2013 Update)”; http://www.cii.co.uk/media/4119720/regulatory_landscape_dec_2012_20_dec_.pdf

70 Mark J. Flannery, “Supervising Bank Safety and Soundness: Some Open Issues”, DRAF, Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco, <http://www.frbsf.org/economic-research/files/flannery.pdf>

71 See *Supra*, note 61, section. A. International Lending Supervision Act of 1983

72 No. 94-1877, 4th Circuit, <http://caselaw.findlaw.com/us-4th-circuit/1337082.html>; Also See *Supra* note 61 section B

73 United States Court of Appeals, fifth court, No. 94-40377, <http://caselaw.findlaw.com/us-5th-circuit/1249163.html>

74 The Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act (GLB Act or GLBA), also known as the Financial Modernization Act of 1999. “Financial Services Modernization Act”, Gramm-Leach-Bliley, Summary of Provisions, <http://www.banking.senate.gov/conf/grmleach.htm>

75 “The Bank Holding Company Act of 1956”, Duke Law Journal, Vol 7:1, 1957, Available at: <http://scholarship.law.duke.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1637&context=dlj>

regulators are not only concerned with financial stability but are also bogged down by costly judicial reviews in vindicating the rights of creditors and depositors. US has a strong adversarial external litigation driven legislative and judicial process (e.g, *SEC v. Bank of America*⁷⁶, *SEC v. Stanford International Bank*⁷⁷, *Deutsche Bank Nat'l Trust Co. v. FDIC*⁷⁸), where as the UK follows a more tightly integrated principle-based risk governance approach that minimizes private litigation and creates efficiencies in time and costs with special attention to consumer protection⁷⁹.

Environmental Regulatory Framework

The British government lacked the underpinning of continental law and much of the government's environmental policy was developed around voluntary agreements until the 1980s. The prevailing lack of transparency generally made it unclear to determine the role of scientists and government officials. This was reflected in the Continental Shelf Act of 1964⁸⁰ which was passed when UK government discovered natural gas under the continental shelf and hurriedly replicated the onshore regulatory regime which included the “IP Code” (Institute of Petroleum Model Code of Safe Practice in the Petroleum Industry)⁸¹. As a result, the offshore Sea Gem drilling rig operated by BP sank in December 1965⁸². From 1954 until 1983, pesticide controls regulating the use and marketing of pesticides in the UK were governed by a voluntary agreements between the government, manufacturers and distributors under the Pesticide Safety Precaution Scheme⁸³. In 1985 this was replaced by a statutory scheme under the Food and Environment Act. However, this scheme was limited to government and industry only.

During the Margaret Thatcher era, wholesale deregulation also reduced budgets of environmental agencies and privatized key utilities such as water and electricity. Statutory form of legislative instruments were enacted, and various environmental agencies were created. Independent approaches

76 Litigation Release No. 21407 / February 4, 2010, <http://www.sec.gov/litigation/litreleases/2010/lr21407.htm>

77 Securities and Exchange Commission v. Stanford International Bank, <http://cdm16064.contentdm.oclc.org/cdm/ref/collection/p266901coll4/id/2876>

78 784 F. SUPP. 2D 1142 (C.D. CAL. 2011), *DEUTSCHE BANK NAT'L TRUST CO. V. FED. DEPOSIT INS. CORP.*, <https://www.casetext.com/case/deutsche-bank-natl-trust-co-v-fed-deposit-ins-corp/>

79 KPMG, UK, “*The Future of Compliance: Compliance functions as strategic partners in the new regulatory world*”, http://www.kpmg.com/UK/en/IssuesAndInsights/ArticlesPublications/Documents/PDF/Advisory/future-of-compliance_web_Acc4.pdf

80 Continental Shelf Act, 1964, c. 29, § 1

81 Petroleum (Production) Regulations, 1935, Stat. R. & O. 1935/426; Regulations, 1964, S.I. 1964/708, sched. 2

82 W.G. Carson, *The Other Price of Britain's Oil: Regulating Safety on Offshore Oil Installations in the British Sector of the North Sea*, 4 *Contemp. Crises* 239, 250 (1980)

83 J.M Barnes, “*The Widespread use of pesticides*”, *J. clin. Path.*, 28, Suppl. (Roy. Coll. Path.), 9, 115-118, MedicalResearchCouncilToxicologyUnit, MRC Laboratories, <http://europepmc.org/articles/PMC1347191/pdf/jclinpath00434-0120.pdf>

among UK's devolved administrations (England, Wales and Scotland) also contributed to increased divergence in the regulatory framework⁸⁴.

UK is also bound by EU environmental laws and is party to international agreements such as Cartagena Protocol on Biodiversity for 'living modified organisms' (GMO)⁸⁵. Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra) and Food Standards Agency together administer national marketing and research of GMO; however, the approvals for marketing is obtained at the EU level (under the Directive 2001/18/EC⁸⁶) while approvals for research and development on GM organisms is obtained from UK ministers⁸⁷. Also, for instance, the IPPC EU Directive in 1996 to prevent air, water, and soil pollutant emissions was translated into the UK Pollution Prevention and Control Act of 1999 (PPC).

Environmental Enforcements in UK

Environment Act 1995 gave enforcement authority to local authorities (such as National Rivers Authorities, Waste Regulation Authorities) and the Environment Agency. The environmental litigation is based on strict liability which requires expert evidence; furthermore, the preference of prevention (*known* risks) first and “precautionary approach” (*unknown* risks) often determines the choice of enforcement⁸⁸ where the Crown Court is referred over for sentencing in the course of a prosecution. Agencies leniently issue a warning, or a caution notice before threatening court action⁸⁹. The maximum fine for most environmental crimes is unusually a maximum of 50,000GBP⁹⁰. Individuals have been discouraged to bring private prosecution against environmental offenders but this

84 For instance, Wales, Sustainable Development Bill 2013 (<http://wales.gov.uk/topics/sustainabledevelopment/?lang=en>); Scotland, Regulatory Reform Bill, SEPA (<http://www.sepa.org.uk>)

85 Levidow, Les (2001). Precautionary uncertainty: regulating GM crops in Europe. *Social Studies of Science*, 31(6), pp. 842–874

86 Directive 2001/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the deliberate release into the environment of genetically modified organisms and repealing Council Directive 90/220/EEC, *Available at*: http://www.biosafety.be/GB/Dir.Eur.GB/Del.Rel./2001_18/2001_18_TC.html

87 Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs, “*Making the food and farming industry more competitive while protecting the environment*”, <https://www.gov.uk/government/policies/making-the-food-and-farming-industry-more-competitive-while-protecting-the-environment/supporting-pages/genetic-modification>

88 Rosie Cooney, “*The Precautionary Principle in Biodiversity Conservation and Natural Resource Management: An issues paper for policy-makers, researchers and practitioners*”, IUCN – The World Conservation Union 2004, *Available at*: <http://data.iucn.org/dbtw-wpd/edocs/pgc-002.pdf>

89 W Benson, L Davis, W Dickson, S France, E Glennie, “*The Effectiveness Of Enforcement Of Environmental Legislation*”, DEFRA, *Available at*: <http://archive.defra.gov.uk/environment/policy/enforcement/pdf/envleg-enforce-wrreport.pdf>

90 The Magistrates’ Association, “*COSTING THE EARTH: guidance for sentencers 2009*”, *Available at*: <http://www.magistrates-association-temp.org.uk/dox/Costing%20the%20Earth%20for%20MA%20with%20cover.pdf>

has been changing since the 1990s⁹¹. *Environment Agency v Milford Haven Port Authority and Andrews*⁹² is a good example of the bureaucratic tardiness of the Environment Agency being challenged. *Greenpeace v Albright and Wilson*⁹³ was the first private prosecution under the Water Act 1989⁹⁴. *Roxburghe v Reigate and Banstead BC*⁹⁵ was the first private prosecution under the anti-litter provision of Environment Protection Act 1990. In *Hart v Anglian Water Services Ltd*⁹⁶, an individual was able to prosecute one of the contractors to Environment Agency under the Water Resources Act 1991. The fine was reduced from 200,000GBP to 60,000GBP in Mr. Hart's case, but generally few environmental private prosecutions are ever successful in record⁹⁷.

While there has been an increase in private prosecution before the magistrate and the jury, there are still industries that are not governed by any statutory legislation. For example, the meat distribution industry, previously regulated by the abolished watchdog Meat Hygiene Agency, currently does not abide by any regulatory controls. Moreover, related enforcement agencies (such as Department of the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs) are limited by the strict liability restrictions in the Food Safety Act 1990 to take any meaningful action⁹⁸.

US Environmental Regime, Standards and Enforcements

United States' modern environmental legislation dates back to 1970, when the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) was created. EPA regulated by identifying an environmental target such as a limit on emissions of a pollutant to water or the air (the 'command'), with penalties that would be imposed if this target is not met (the 'control')⁹⁹. After the Ronald Reagan era¹⁰⁰ of deregulation, the regulators turned to 'mimicking the market' approach. The Acid Rain Program, which was established in the USA by the Clean Air Act Amendments of 1990: Industry-wide cap on emissions of sulphur

91 Environmental Law (6th edn, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2006), p.294

92 *Environment Agency v Milford Haven Port Authority and Andrews* [1999] 1 Lloyd's L.R. 673 at 679

93 [1991] 3 L.M.E.L.R. 170

94 Water Act, 1989, <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1989/15>

95 [1992] 4 L.M.E.L.R. 101

96 [2003] EWCA Crim 2243; [2004] Env. L.R. 10

97 Neil Parpworth, "Enforcing environmental laws: the role of the private prosecution", *Journal of Planning & Environment Law*, 2007.

98 Zia Akhtar, "Illicit Meat, European Directives and Enforcement Powers in the UK", 2011 Eur. Food & Feed L. Rev. 336 (2011)

99 Neil Gunningham, "Environment Law, Regulation and Governance: Shifting Architectures", *Journal of Environmental Law* (2009) 21 (2): 179-212. doi: 10.1093/jel/eqp011

100 Matthew Sherman, "A Short History of Financial Deregulation in the United States", 2009, Center for Economic and Policy Research, Available at: <http://www.cepr.net/documents/publications/dereg-timeline-2009-07.pdf>

dioxide was set, operators affected were allowed to trade emissions and preserve cost-efficiency¹⁰¹. This approach was the hallmark of self-regulation, voluntary codes, environmental charters, co-regulation, covenants and negotiated environmental agreements. However, it was soon discovered that performance standards were only incentives to meet minimum standards but not an encouragement to engage in innovation.

The Clinton-Gore administration, began experimenting with an innovative approach to standard setting variously termed ‘process-based’, ‘systems-based’ or ‘management based’ regulation¹⁰². There was little empirical evidence of sustainable and profitable outcomes to environmental compliances, and such regulations were seen as anti-competitive and burdensome¹⁰³. The ‘new environmental governance’ in US that has emerged involves collaboration between a diversity of private, public and non-government stakeholders, acting together towards mutually negotiated goals. This is reflected in Habitat Conservation Plans under the Endangered Species Act and in the Chesapeake Bay and San Francisco Bay Delta Programmes¹⁰⁴.

US Agency Struggles

Conflicts among federal, and state regulatory officials over biotechnology is common because many agencies may have jurisdiction over a genetically altered product. The federal agencies that can become involved include the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA), Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA), National Institutes of Health (NIH), and Food and Drug Administration (FDA)¹⁰⁵. Genentech suffered delays and expenses while agencies argued if their new product was “veterinary biologic” under USDA, or “animal drug” under FDA. The 2010 Salmonella¹⁰⁶ outbreak was also rooted in structural issues stemming from failures of multiple agencies: FDA, USDA, Food Safety and Inspection Service (FSIS), Health Inspection Service

101 See *Supra* note 95, Page 186-187

102 C Coglianese and D Lazar, ‘Management-Based Regulation: Prescribing Private Management to Achieve Public Goals’ (2003) 37 *Law and Society Review* 691 ; See *Supra* 94, C. *Law, Regulation and Governance?*

103 A Hoffman, *From Heresy to Dogma: An Institutional History of Corporate Environmentalism*, (Stanford Business Books, Stanford 2001)

104 B Karkkainen, ‘Collaborative Ecosystem Governance: Scale, Complexity, and Dynamism’ (2001/2002) 21 *Virginia Environmental Law Journal* 189; J Freeman and D Farber, ‘Modular Environmental Regulation’ (2005) 54 *Duke Law Journal* 795

105 ‘*The Liability and Regulatory Threat to Biotech*’, Center for Legal Policy at the Manhattan Institute, http://www.manhattan-institute.org/html/cjm_6.htm

106 Food & Drug Admin. *Salmonella Enteritidis Outbreak in Shell Eggs*, U.S. DEP’T OF HEALTH & HUMAN SERV. (Nov. 30, 2010), <http://www.fda.gov/food/newsevents/whatsnewinfood/ucm222684.htm>

(APHIS), and Agricultural Marketing Service (AMS)¹⁰⁷. This occurred despite the 2006 *E. coli* O157:H7 outbreak that prompted the “*Food Safety: Improvements Needed in FDA Oversight of Fresh Produce*” report in 2008¹⁰⁸. Furthermore, a joint study between EPA and UK EA concluded that the US environment protection through permits and licensing system is weak and outdated compared to the EU-mandated Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control (IPPC) permitting system as implemented in the UK¹⁰⁹.

A “coordinated framework” of FDA, EPA and USDA regime currently regulates GM foods where FDA places the ultimate responsibility on the producer under section 402(a)(1)¹¹⁰ to ensure food safety. There is also currently no regulatory scheme requiring GM foods to be tested to evaluate safety for human consumption¹¹¹.

Intellectual Property, FDI and Trade

Monsanto, for example, is one of the biggest manufacturer of agricultural biotechnology based in the United States that benefits from being in the jurisdiction. While EU is a large consumer market for GMO, the threat of the “precautionary approach” in the EU has made United States relatively attractive for other proprietary seed manufactures as well: Cargill, ADM, Bunge, Bayer, BASF and Dow AgroSciences¹¹². Additionally, it should be noted that US provides a strong IP regime to protect patent products such as GMOs¹¹³. Based on the OECD 2000 indicators UK does not have any non-tariff barriers such as foreign ownership, discriminatory procedures, and has low

107 U.S. GEN. ACCOUNTING OFFICE, GAO/RCED-99-184, FOOD SAFETY: U.S. LACKS A CONSISTENT FARM-TO-TABLE APPROACH TO EGG SAFETY 2 (July 1, 1999), available at <http://archive.gao.gov/f0902b/162324.pdf>.

108 GAO, “FOOD SAFETY Improvements Needed in FDA Oversight of Fresh Produce”, 2008, GAO-08-1047, Available at: <http://www.gao.gov/new.items/d081047.pdf>

109 “*An In-depth Look at the United Kingdom Integrated Permitting System Exploring Global Environmental Protection Perspectives*”, July 2008, US Environmental Protection Agency Office of Policy, Economics & Innovation National Center for Environmental Innovation. Available at: <http://www.epa.gov/osem/integrated/pdf/IntPermittingRpt.pdf>

110 FDA&C, Chapter IV: Food, <http://www.fda.gov/RegulatoryInformation/Legislation/FederalFoodDrugandCosmeticActFDCAct/FDCActChapterIVFood/>; See also, <http://www.gpo.gov/fdsys/pkg/USCODE-2010-title21/html/USCODE-2010-title21-chap9-subchapIV-sec343.htm>

111 Peter Melchett, The pro-GM lobby's seven sins against science

<http://www.soilassociation.org/motherearth/viewarticle/articleid/4752/the-pr-12/2012>

112 The Guardian, “*It is too late to shut the door on GM foods*”, Felicity Lawrence, 16, October, 2009,

<http://www.theguardian.com/environment/2009/oct/16/too-late-to-stop-gm>

113 Reuters, “*U.S. farmer lawsuit filed against Monsanto over GMO wheat*”, Carey Gillam, Thursday, June 6, 2013,

<http://www.reuters.com/article/2013/06/06/us-usa-monsanto-lawsuit-idUSBRE9530U320130606>; See

MONSANTO.COM, Newsroom, “*Why Does Monsanto Sue Farmers Who Save Seeds?*”,

<http://www.monsanto.com/newsviews/Pages/why-does-monsanto-sue-farmers-who-save-seeds.aspx>

entrepreneurial license and permits regulations in contrast with the US¹¹⁴. While the scope of state control is higher in the US, the use of command-and-control regulation is more prevalent in the United Kingdom¹¹⁵.

Conclusion

Over the last 40 years, UK and the US regulatory environment has moved between varying degrees of “command and control” regulation to co-regulation and self-regulation. While the UK and EU has seen strong leadership in stricter environmental regulatory regimes, the US struggles with overlapping federal and state agencies operating in an adversarial litigation driven environment. There have also been greater statutory structural reforms in the financial sector in the United Kingdom compared to the US where it is far easier to strike down legislation in judicial reviews. This is reflected, for example, in the new consultative structural integration between Bank of England and the new regulatory agencies. With a much more flexible self-regulated financial and environmental regulatory environment, the United States often presents a landscape of regulatory uncertainty while the UK generally provides a far more predictable regulatory environment. UK governs in a “risk-management” style of “prevention” and “precaution” placing the burden of proof on corporations, producers, and distributors, while the US requires scientific proof to challenge a *de facto* position.

114 Nicoletti, Scarpetta & Boylaud, OECD Working Paper 226, (2000)

115 Nicoletti, Scarpetta & Boylaud, OECD Working Paper 226, (2000), Table A2.2.1, Table A2.7

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Books

Brickman, R., Jasanoff, S., & Ilgen, T. (1985). *Controlling Chemicals: The politics of regulation in Europe and the United States*. Ithaca, NY, Cornell University Press.

Chatfield M (1922) *A History of Accounting Thought*, New York: Krieger

David Andrew Singe (2007), *Regulating Capital: Setting Standards for the International Financial System*

David Sciulli, Amitai Etzioni, *Macro Socio-economics: From Theory to Activism*

Kelmen, S.(1981). *Regulating America, regulating Sweden: A comparative study of occupational safety and health policy*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

Moran, Michael, *The British Regulatory State: High Modernism and Hyper Innovation*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2003, P 31-42

Vogel, D. (1995), *Trading up: consumer and environmental regulation in a global economy*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Journals / Articles

Andrew P. Morriss, Bruce Yandle, Andrew Dorchak, “Choosing How to Regulate”, Harvard Environmental Law Review, Vol. 29. 2005. Available at:

http://www.law.harvard.edu/students/orgs/elr/vol29_1/morriss.pdf

Franklin R. Edwards, Hedge Fund and the Collapse of Long-Term Capital Management, Journal of Economic Perspectives – Vol. 13, Number, 2, Spring 1999, P 189-210, Available at:

http://www0.gsb.columbia.edu/faculty/fedwards/papers/Hedge_Funds_&_the_Collapse_of_LTCM.pdf

Gunningham, N., and Rees. J., (1997), Industry Self Regulation, An Institutional Perspective, Law and Policy, Vol. 19, Issue, p. 363-414

Iain McLean (2002), The origin and strange history of regulation in the UK: three case studies in search of a theory, ESF/SCSS Exploratory Workshop: The Politics of Regulation, Barcelona

Neil Gunningham, “Environment Law, Regulation and Governance: Shifting Architectures”, Journal of Environmental Law (2009) 21 (2): 179-212. doi: 10.1093/jel/eqp011

Neil Parpworth, “Enforcing environmental laws: the role of the private prosecution”, Journal of Planning & Environment Law, 2007

Zia Akhtar, “Illicit Meat, European Directives and Enforcement Powers in the UK”, 2011 Eur. Food & Feed L. Rev. 336 (2011)